

A Study of Anhydro-base Formation from Flavylium Salts

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Contrary to earlier belief, it is shown that the 7-hydroxyl undergoes loss of proton in preference to the 4'-hydroxyl during anhydro-base formation from flavylium salts. This gives an insight into the biogenesis of carajurin (XX) and carajurone (XIX).

Most of the naturally occurring flavylium salts (anthocyanidins) have a hydroxy group in the 3-position. Only a few of them are devoid of this and the first example of this type to be discovered was gesneridin (apigeninidin, 5,7,4'-trihydroxyflavylium salt) from the flowers of orange-coloured *Gesnera fulgens*¹. More recently, luteolinidin (5, 7, 3', 4'-tetrahydroxyflavylium salt) has been isolated from bright scarlet petals of *Gesnera cardinals*² and 5,7,3',4',5'-pentahydroxyflavylium salt has been detected on paper chromatogram as a substance present in tea leaves³.

If a flavylium salt (I) has a free hydroxyl in any of the four positions (5,7,2', or 4'), it is converted into an anhydro-colour base having a quinonoid structure (II, III, IV, or V) on treatment with either cold aqueous sodium acetate or aqueous pyridine or even boiling water. Its formation can be explained on the basis that the basic reagent extracts a proton from one of the hydroxyls in favourable positions (5,7,2', or 4') of the flavylium ion which is capable of undergoing the electromeric change as illustrated in formulæ (I a and I b). The quinonoid product is called an anhydro-base because it could arise by the loss of water from the flavylium hydroxide or from the carbinol (see formula VII) corresponding to the flavylium salt.

1. Robinson, Robinson, and Todd, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 809.
2. Harborne, *Chem. & Ind.*, 1960, 229.
3. Roberts and William, *J. Sci. Food Agric.*, 1958, 9, 217; Virataz *et al.*, *J. Chromatog.*, 1959, 2, 173.

The presence or absence of a free hydroxyl in the 3-position makes a great difference. In its absence, the anhydro-base becomes stable. On the other hand, a hydroxy group in the 3-position of an anhydro-base (VI) favours the formation of a pseudo-base (VII a or VII b) which could be obtained directly from the flavylum salts by treatment with water or ethanol. The greater stability of the pseudo-base in this case may be attributed to the readiness with which the initial flaven-diol (VII) can tautomerise into a more stable keto structure (VIII a or VIII b)⁴. It may be emphasized that the nonformation of a ψ -base has been considered earlier to be an evidence for the absence of a 3-hydroxyl in the case of natural anhydro-bases like carajurin and carajurone⁵.

A search in the literature shows that even among the anhydro-bases having no 3-hydroxyl, considerable difference exists not only in colour but also in stability. The colour bases from 2'-hydroxyflavylum salts are reported to be violet compounds⁶ and those derived from 5-hydroxyl salts are coloured bluish violet⁷ and both of them are highly unstable

4. Seshadri, *Festschrift Arthur Stoll* (1957), Birkhauser AG, Basel, p. 318.

5. Chapman *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 3015.

6. Irvine and Robinson, *ibid.*, 1927, 2086.

7. Collie and White, *ibid.*, 1915, 107, 369; Brockmann and Junge, *Ber.*, 1943, 76B, 1028; 1944, 77B, 44; Brockmann *et al.*, *Ber.*, 1944, 77B, 347.

and lose colour readily even in water or ethanol. Anhydro-bases from 4'-hydroxyflavylium salts are dark violet solids existing mainly as quinhydrone⁶ whereas those obtained from 7-hydroxyflavylium salts are described as red solids^{7,8} and they are fairly stable. The labile nature of the first two types of colour bases can be attributed to the presence of the unfavourable *o*-quinonoid structure in contrast to the *p*-quinonoid structure possessed by the latter two.

No experimental work, however, seems to have been done on the problem as to which particular hydroxyl takes part in the quinonoid formation when two or more than two hydroxyls are present among the four positions, 5, 7, 2', and 4'. Since *o*-quinonoid forms are considerably less stable, it could be expected on grounds of stability that 5- and 2'-hydroxy groups will not effectively compete with the 7- and 4'-hydroxyls. But the choice has to be made between the latter two possibilities. In earlier publications, 4'-hydroxyl has generally been preferred to the 7-hydroxyl for the loss of a proton to form an anhydro-base though there was no definite evidence. For example, 4'-keto structures (IX and X) have been given for the colour bases obtained from malvin⁹ and cyanidin^{9a} respectively.

Recently Seshadri⁴, based on certain preliminary results, suggested that these anhydro-bases should have the 7-keto structures instead of the 4'-keto ones. The main considerations that led him to take this view were: (i) the naturally occurring colour bases, viz., carajurin, carajurone, dracorhodin, dracorubin, santalin, and santarubin have all got the keto group in the 7 position; (ii) these are characterised by stability and deep red colour like the synthetic 7-anhydro-bases; (iii) these have the 4'-position either free or substituted by a methoxyl. It is the object of the present work to examine this question fully.

The anhydro-base (anhydro-7,4'-dihydroxyflaven-4 or 2-ol, XII a) has now been prepared from 7,4'-dihydroxyflavylium chloride (XIa). The free hydroxy group in the anhydro-base has been methylated and for this, wet methylation using aqueous potassium carbonate in inert atmosphere is found to be the most satisfactory. The resulting product has been compared with two possible alternative anhydro-bases (XIIIa) and (XVIa), prepared unambiguously from 7-hydroxy-4'-methoxyflavylium chloride (XIVa) and 4'-hydroxy-7-methoxyflavylium chloride (XVa) respectively. The methylated anhydro-base is found to be identical with (XIIIa) in paper chromatography as well as in stability. Further confirmation of the 7-keto structure is provided by alkali fission of the methylated colour base and identification of anisic acid as the fission product.

8. Hirst, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 2490.

9. Robinson and Todd, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 2293.

9a. Robinson, Indian Association for the Cultivation of Science, Calcutta, Special Publication No. 4, 1950.

[For XI and XII: a, R=H; b, R=OH].

[For XIII to XVI: a, R=H; b, R=OMe].

As another example, anhydro-7,3',4'-trihydroxyflaven-4 or-2-ol (XII b) has also been examined. Its methylation was found to be comparatively difficult. The product was compared with anhydro-7-hydroxy-3',4'-dimethoxyflaven-4 or-2-ol (XIII b) and anhydro-7,3'-dimethoxy-4'-hydroxyflaven-4 or-2-ol (XVI b) and it was found to agree with the former anhydro-base (XIIIb) in its properties.

There seems to be considerable difference between the anhydro-bases having keto groups in the 4'- and 7-positions. The colour of the former fades when either stored or kept in contact with water and hydroxylic solvents even for some time, whereas the latter is not appreciably affected. Even 7-keto bases, as far as the two examples studied in the present work are concerned, undergo change when kept in contact with water, ethanol, pyridine, or sodium acetate solution at room temperature for a longer period and the change becomes faster by raising the temperature. Several naturally occurring anhydro-bases having 7-keto group have, however, been found to be stable under these conditions.

From the above experiments it could be concluded that if available free, the 7-hydroxyl is definitely preferred to 4'-hydroxyl for the loss of a proton during anhydro-base formation;

this could be expected to happen in Nature also. Further methylation of the 4'-hydroxyl in natural compounds seems to be a subsequent process. This probably becomes more facile after the formation of the 7-keto compound because the 4'-hydroxyl then becomes more acidic by conjugation with the carbonyl group (for vinylogy see formula XVIII). Thus the steps indicated in formulas (XVIII-XX) could be proposed for the biogenesis of the two pigments of *Bignonia chica*, carajurin (XX) and carajurone (XIX). The 5-hydroxyl, not being at the terminus of the conjugation, may be less active as compared with the 4'-hydroxyl which is methylated first and hence carajurone represents an intermediate stage. Regarding earlier stages, a new recent observation made by Krishnamurty *et al.*¹⁰ is of significance. It has been shown that 3-hydroxyflavanones in the form of acetates can undergo isomeric change in the laboratory in the presence of a base catalyst to yield acetates of the corresponding ψ -bases of anthocyanidins. This appears to provide a model for biogenesis and would suggest that 3-hydroxyflavanones could directly give rise to anthocyanidins in plants. In analogous cases of flavanones without this 3-hydroxyl, the same change could be expected under suitable conditions (not yet determined) to yield anhydro-bases by loss of water since in these cases the ψ -bases (see XVIIb) will be unstable. Consequently isocarthamidin (XVII a) could be accepted as the origin of carajurin and carajurone, as shown below.

EXPERIMENTAL

Light absorption data are, unless otherwise stated, taken in benzene solution containing a few drops of methanol and recorded in the order of their decreasing intensity; log ϵ values are not given because of the difficulty of solubility of anhydro-bases. The irrigating solvent for circular paper chromatography is the upper layer of phenol-water (1:2.5) and the ring on the chromatogram has been marked as seen in the ultraviolet light. The solvent used for flavylum salt condensation is uniformly anhydrous acetic acid even in known preparations. Melting points of anhydro-bases are found to be indistinct and hence omitted. Analytical values are reported on air-dried samples because of their instability at higher temperatures; on this account, the analytical values are not quite satisfactory.

Anhydro-7,4'-dihydroxyflaven-(4 or 2)-ol (XII a).—7,4'-Dihydroxyflavylium chloride (XI a) (1g.) was dissolved in warm 1% HCl, cooled, and treated gradually with a saturated aqueous solution of sodium acetate when a scarlet-coloured anhydro-base (0.9 g.) separated. It was filtered, washed with water, and dried *in vacuo*. R_F 0.62 at 36°; λ_{max} 288, 355, and 495 m μ ; λ_{min} 305 and 420 m μ . (Found: C, 73.1; H, 4.4. $C_{15}H_{10}O_3$, $\frac{1}{2}$ H₂O requires C, 72.9; H, 4.5%).

Methylation and Formation of Anhydro-7-hydroxy-4'-methoxyflaven-(4 or 2)-ol (XIIIa).—The above anhydro-base (1g.) was dissolved in the minimum amount of 5% aqueous potassium carbonate. Air was swept off with nitrogen and dimethyl sulphate (2.1 ml) was added slowly to the above stirred solution. After 3 hours the solution was neutralised and the precipitate collected, dried, and crystallised from benzene containing a few drops of methanol when fine red needles (0.4 g.) separated; m.p. 128-30°. The melting point was undepressed by admixture with anhydro-7-hydroxy-4'-methoxyflaven-(4 or 2)-ol (XIIIa) (see Brockmann *et al.*⁷) prepared from 7-hydroxy-4'-methoxyflavylium chloride (XIVa). The flavylium chloride (XIVa) itself was prepared as described by Freudenberg *et al.*¹². Complete identity of the methylated anhydro-base with the authentic sample was also found in the following properties: R_F 0.50 at 36°; λ_{max} 348, 295, and 498 m μ ; λ_{min} 300 and 415 m μ .

Alkali fission of the methylated anhydro-base (XIIIa) (0.5 g.) was accomplished by refluxing with aqueous 5% KOH solution (15 ml) for 6 hours in a silver flask. The mixture was cooled, acidified, and extracted with ether. The ether layer was in turn extracted with sodium bicarbonate solution which on acidification yielded colorless needles, m.p. 184° alone or when mixed with an authentic sample of anisic acid.

Anhydro-4'-hydroxy-7-methoxyflaven-(4 or 2)-ol (XVIa).—*p*-Methoxysalicylaldehyde required for this preparation was prepared earlier by methylation of β -resorcyaldehyde either with dimethyl sulphate and EtOH-KOH¹³ or with diazomethane¹⁴. It has been found now that methylation with dimethyl sulphate under dry conditions affords good yields as mentioned below. A solution of β -resorcyaldehyde (10 g.) in dry acetone (100 ml) was heated with dimethyl sulphate (7.6 ml) and potassium carbonate (30g.) for 3 hours. The acetone solution was concentrated and subjected to steam distillation when *p*-methoxysalicylaldehyde (4 g.) separated as white shining needles from the steam distillate, m.p. 40-42°. It was converted into 7-methoxy-4'-hydroxyflavylium chloride (XVa) as described by Freudenberg *et al.*¹² and subsequently into its anhydro-base as mentioned in a similar case earlier, but avoiding excess of sodium acetate and performing the reaction at 0-5°. The anhydro-base obtained was highly unstable in hydroxylic solvents and practically insoluble in non-hydroxylic solvents. Hence it could neither be crystallised nor spectroscopically examined; R_F 0.41 at 36°.

Anhydro-7,3',4'-trihydroxyflaven-(4 or 2)-ol (XII b).—Butinidin chloride (XI b), prepared from β -resorcyaldehyde and 3,4-dihydroxyacetophenone¹⁵ by the method of

11. Freudenberg and Weinges, *Annalen*, 1954, 590, 140.

12. *Ber.*, 1957, 90, 957.

13. Ott and Nauen, *Ber.*, 1922, 55, 920.

14. Offe and Jatzkowitz, *Ber.*, 1947, 80, 469.

15. Moed *et al.*, *Rec. trav. Chim.*, 1958, 77, 278.

Freudenberg and Maitland¹⁶ was converted into its anhydro-base (XII b) as described earlier for a similar case. It was obtained as a scarlet solid; R_F 0.36 at 33°; λ_{max} 290, 350, and 495 m μ ; λ_{min} 302 and 420 m μ . (Found: C, 67.9; H, 4.9. $C_{13}H_{10}O_4$, † H_2O requires C, 68.4; H, 4.2%).

Methylation and Formation of Anhydro-7-hydroxy-3',4'-dimethoxyflaven-(4 or 2)-ol (XIIIb).—The above anhydro-base (1g.) was methylated with aqueous potassium carbonate and dimethyl sulphate in nitrogen atmosphere as mentioned in an earlier case. Neutralisation of the solution at 0° gave a deeply coloured product (0.4g.); R_F 0.40 at 33°; λ_{max} 355, 288, and 495 m μ ; λ_{min} 305 and 420 m μ . (Found: C, 64.3; H, 6.1. $C_{17}H_{14}O_4$, 2 H_2O requires C, 64.2; H, 5.7%). In all these properties it agrees with anhydro-7-hydroxy-3', 4'-dimethoxyflaven-(4 or 2)-ol (XIII b) prepared from red-coloured 7-hydroxy-3',4'-dimethoxyflavylium salt¹⁷ (XIV b) by the usual method.

4'-Hydroxy-7,3'-dimethoxyflavylium Chloride (XV b).—*p*-Methoxysalicylaldehyde (0.9g.) and acetovanillone¹⁸ (0.95 g.) were dissolved in anhydrous acetic acid (20 ml) and the solution saturated with dry hydrogen chloride at 5-10° during 4 hours. After leaving it at room temperature for 24 hours, dry ether was added to precipitate the flavylium chloride. It was filtered, washed with ether, and crystallised from 5% HCl when the chloride (XVb) (1g.) separated as scarlet crystals with greenish yellow reflex, m.p. 195° (decomp.). (Found: C, 57.5; H, 6.1. $C_{17}H_{15}O_4Cl$, 2 H_2O requires C, 57.6; H, 5.4%).

Anhydro-4'-hydroxy-7,3'-dimethoxyflaven-(4 or 2)-ol (XVI b).—Ice-cold aqueous sodium acetate solution was added dropwise to 1% HCl solution of the above flavylium salt (0.5g.) at 0° until no more precipitation took place. Excess of sodium acetate was judiciously avoided and the precipitate (0.45 g.) immediately filtered. It was found to be unstable even in the solid state; R_F 0.27 at 33°.

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16. *Annalen*, 1934, 510, 193.

17. Robertson and Robinson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 1951.

18. Reichstein, *Helv. Chem. Acta*, 1927, 10, 392.